

CP Violation from Co-bimaximality Neutrino Mixing Pattern above the GUT Scale

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Abstract: We consider non-reormalizable interaction term as a perturbation of the conventional neutrino mass matrix. Quantum gravitational (Planck scale) effects lead to an effective $SU(2)_L \times U(1)$ invariant dimension-5 Lagrangian involving neutrino and Higgs fields, which gives rise to additional terms in neutrino mass matrix. There additional term can be considered to be perturbation of the GUT scale Co-bimaximal neutrino mass matrix. In particular, for the θ'_{13} range $9.81^\circ - 10.02^\circ$, indicates the existence of CP violating violatiob above the GUT scale. We assume that the gravitational interaction is flavor blind. In this paper, we further investigate the possibility of CP violation exist from Quantum gravity.

Keywords: CP Violation, Co-bimaximal Neutrino Mixing, GUT Scale

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1. Introduction

The hypothesis of neutrino oscillation, impressive advance have been made to understand the phenomenology of neutrino oscillation through solar neutrino, atmospheric neutrino, reactor neutrino and accelerator neutrino experiments. These experiments enabling the determination of the Maki-Nakigawa Sakata (MNS) lepton mixing matrix. The main physical goal in future experiment are the determination of the unknown parameter θ_{13} . In particular, the observation of δ is quite interesting for

the point of view that δ related to the origin of the matter in the universe. CP violation is one of the most important problem in particle physics [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. One of the most important parameter in neutrino physics is the magnitude of mixing angle θ_{13} and CP phase δ . The search for CP violation is great interest to various aspects of neutrino physics. CP violation in the next generation of long baseline oscillation experiments. At present information regarding θ_{13} , we have an upper bound that is bases on the CHOOZ experiment [6], that is $\theta_{13} \leq 13^\circ$ at 3 sigmas.

The main physical goal in future experiment are the determination of the CP phase. In particular, the observation of δ is quite interesting for the point of view that δ related to the origin of the matter in the universe. The determination of δ is the final goal of the future experiments. We get the analytical expression for $\Delta P(\alpha, \beta)$ using the usual form of the MNS matrix parametrization.

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} c_{12}c_{13} & s_{12}c_{13} & s_{13}e^{-i\delta} \\ -s_{12}c_{23} - c_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & c_{12}c_{23} - s_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & s_{23}c_{13} \\ s_{12}s_{23} - c_{12}c_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & -c_{12}s_{23} - s_{12}s_{13}s_{23}e^{i\delta} & c_{23}s_{13} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where c and s denoted the cosine and sine of the respective notation, thus $\Delta P(\alpha, \beta)$ in vacuum can be written as

$$\Delta P(\alpha, \beta) = 16J (\sin\Delta_{21}\sin\Delta_{32}\sin\Delta_{31}). \quad (2)$$

Here α and β denote different neutrino or anti-neutrino favour where

$$\Delta_{ij} = 1.27 \left(\frac{\Delta_{ij}}{eV^2} \right) \left(\frac{L}{Km} \right) \left(\frac{1GeV}{E} \right), \quad (3)$$

$\Delta_{ij} = (m_i^2 - m_j^2)$ is the difference of i th and j th vacuum mass square eigen value, E is the neutrino energy and L is the travel distance and the well-known Jarlskog determinant [5], J is the standard mixing parametrization is given by

$$\begin{aligned} J &= Im (U_{e1}U_{e2}^*U_{\mu1}^*U_{\mu2}) \\ &= \frac{1}{8} \sin 2\theta_{12} \sin 2\theta_{23} \sin 2\theta_{13} \cos \theta_{13} \sin \delta, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

and the asymmetry parameter suggested by Cabibbo [5], as an alternative to measure CP violation in the lepton sector.

$$A_{cp} = \frac{\Delta P}{P(\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e) - P(\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e)}, \tag{5}$$

In this paper, we discuss the possibility of CP violation arises from physics above the Grand Unified Theory (GUT) scale. In Section 2, we outline the neutrino mixing parameter due to Planck scale effects. In Section 3, numerical result and section 4 is devoted to the conclusions.

2. Neutrino Oscillation Parameter due to Planck Scale Effects

The neutrino mass matrix is assumed to be generated by the see saw mechanism [7, 8, 9]. We assume that the dominant part of neutrino mass matrix arise due to GUT scale operators and the lead to Co-bimaximal mixing. The effective gravitational interaction of neutrino with Higgs field can be expressed as $SU(2)_L \times U(1)$ invariant dimension-5 operator [10],

$$L_{grav} = \frac{\lambda_{\alpha\beta}}{M_{pl}} (\psi_{A\alpha} \epsilon \psi_C) C_{ab}^{-1} (\psi_{B\beta} \epsilon_{BD} \psi_D) + h.c. \tag{6}$$

Here and everywhere we use Greek indices α, β for the flavor states and Latin indices i, j, k for the mass states. In the above equation $\psi_\alpha = (\nu_\alpha, l_\alpha)$ is the lepton doublet, $\varphi = (\varphi^+, \varphi^0)$ is the Higgs doublet and $M_{pl} = 1.2 \times 10^{19}$ GeV is the Planck mass λ is a 3×3 matrix in a flavor space with each elements $O(1)$. The Lorentz indices $a, b = 1, 2, 3, 4$ are contracted with the charge conjugation matrix C and the $SU(2)_L$ isospin indices $A, B, C, D = 1, 2$ are contracted with $\epsilon = i\sigma_2, \sigma_m$ ($m = 1, 2, 3$) are the Pauli matrices. After spontaneous electroweak symmetry breaking the Lagrangian in Eq.(6) generated additional term of neutrino mass matrix

$$L_{mass} = \frac{v^2}{M_{pl}} \lambda_{\alpha\beta} \nu_\alpha C^{-1} \nu_\beta, \tag{7}$$

where $v = 174$ GeV is the VEV of electroweak symmetric breaking. We assume that the gravitational interaction is “flavor blind” that is $\lambda_{\alpha\beta}$ is independent of α, β indices. Thus the Planck scale contribution to the neutrino mass matrix is

$$\mu\lambda = \mu \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \tag{8}$$

where the scale μ is

$$\mu = \frac{v^2}{M_{pl}} = 2.5 \times 10^{-6} eV. \tag{9}$$

We take Eq.(7) as perturbation to the main part of the neutrino mass matrix, that is generated by GUT dynamics. To calculate the effects of perturbation on neutrino observables. A natural assumption is that unperturbed (0^{th} order mass matrix) M is given by

$$M = U^* \text{diag}(M_i) U^\dagger, \tag{10}$$

where, U_{ai} is the usual mixing matrix and M_i , the neutrino masses is generated by Grand unified theory. Most of the parameter related to neutrino oscillation are known, the major expectation is given by the mixing elements U_{e3} . We adopt the usual parametrization.

$$\frac{|U_{e2}|}{|U_{e1}|} = \tan\theta_{12}, \tag{11}$$

$$\frac{|U_{\mu3}|}{|U_{\tau3}|} = \tan\theta_{23}, \tag{12}$$

$$|U_{e3}| = \sin\theta_{13}. \tag{13}$$

In term of the above mixing angles, the mixing matrix is

$$U = \text{diag}(e^{if_1}, e^{if_2}, e^{if_3}) R(\theta_{23}) \Delta R(\theta_{13}) \Delta^* R(\theta_{12}) \text{diag}(e^{ia_1}, e^{ia_2}, 1). \tag{14}$$

The matrix $\Delta = \text{diag}(e^{\frac{i\delta}{2}}, 1, e^{-\frac{i\delta}{2}})$ contains the Dirac phase. This leads to CP violation in neutrino oscillation a_1 and a_2 are the so called Majoring phase, which effects the neutrino less double beta decay. f_1, f_2 and f_3 are usually absorbed as a part of the definition of the charge lepton field. Planck scale effects will add other contribution to the mass matrix that gives the new mixing matrix can be written as [9]

$$U' = U(1 + i\delta\theta),$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} U_{e1} & U_{e2} & U_{e3} \\ U_{\mu1} & U_{\mu2} & U_{\mu3} \\ U_{\tau1} & U_{\tau2} & U_{\tau3} \end{pmatrix} + i \begin{pmatrix} U_{e2}\delta\theta_{12}^* + U_{e3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{e1}\delta\theta_{12} + U_{e3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{e1}\delta\theta_{13} + U_{e3}\delta\theta_{23}^* \\ U_{\mu2}\delta\theta_{12}^* + U_{\mu3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{\mu1}\delta\theta_{12} + U_{\mu3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{\mu1}\delta\theta_{13} + U_{\mu3}\delta\theta_{23}^* \\ U_{\tau2}\delta\theta_{12}^* + U_{\tau3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{\tau1}\delta\theta_{12} + U_{\tau3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{\tau1}\delta\theta_{13} + U_{\tau3}\delta\theta_{23}^* \end{pmatrix}. \tag{15}$$

Where $\delta\theta$ is a hermit ion matrix that is first order in μ [9]. The first order mass square difference $\Delta M_{ij}^2 = \Delta M_i^2 - \Delta M_j^2$ get modified [9] as

$$\Delta M_{ij}^{\prime 2} = \Delta M_{ij}^2 + 2(M_i \text{Re}(m_{ii}) - M_j \text{Re}(m_{jj})), \tag{16}$$

Where

$$m = \mu U^t \lambda U,$$

$$\mu = \frac{v^2}{M_{pl}} = 2.5 \times 10^{-6} eV.$$

The change in the elements of the mixing matrix, which we parametrized by $\delta\theta$ [9], is given by

$$\delta\theta_{ij} = \frac{i \text{Re}(m_{jj})(M_i + M_j) - \text{Im}(m_{jj})(M_i - M_j)}{\Delta M_{ij}^{\prime 2}}. \tag{17}$$

The above equation determine only the off diagonal elements of matrix $\delta\theta_{ij}$. The diagonal element of $\delta\theta_{ij}$ can be set to zero by phase invariance. Using Eq(15), we can calculate neutrino mixing angle due to Planck scale effects,

$$\frac{|U'_{e2}|}{|U'_{e1}|} = \tan\theta'_{12}, \tag{18}$$

$$\frac{|U'_{\mu 3}|}{|U'_{\tau 3}|} = \tan\theta'_{23}, \tag{19}$$

$$|U'_{e3}| = \sin\theta'_{13} \tag{20}$$

$$J'_{cp} = \frac{1}{8} \sin 2\theta'_{12} \sin 2\theta'_{23} \sin 2\theta'_{13} \cos\theta'_{13} \sin\delta, \tag{21}$$

For degenerate neutrinos, $M_3 = M_1 \cong M_3 - M_2 \gg M_2 - M_1$, because $\Delta_{31} \cong \Delta_{32} \gg \Delta_{21}$. Thus, from the above set of equations, we see that U'_{e1} and U'_{e2} are much larger than U'_{e3} , $U'_{\mu 3}$ and $U'_{\tau 3}$. Hence we can expect much larger change in θ_{12} compared to θ_{13} and θ_{23} [12]. As one can see from the above expression of mixing angle due to Planck scale effects, depends on new contribution of mixing matrix $U' = U(1 + i\delta\theta)$. The above statements are not dependent on the exact form of the matrix λ given in Eq.(8). They hold true for any form of λ , as long as all its elements are of order 1.

3. Numerical Results

We assume that, just above the electroweak breaking scale, the neutrino masses are nearly degenerate and the mixing are Co-bimaximal, with the value of the mixing angle as $\theta_{13} \neq 0^\circ = 10^\circ, \theta_{23} = \frac{\pi}{4}, \tan\theta_{12}^2 = \frac{1-3\sin\theta_{13}^2}{2}, \theta_{12} = 34^\circ$ and Dirac phase $\delta = \pm \frac{\pi}{2}$. Taking the common degenerate neutrino mass to be 2eV, which is the upper limit coming from tritium beta decay [13]. We compute the modified mixing angles using Eq.(18s) to Eq.(21). We have taken $\Delta_{31} = 0.002\text{eV}^2$ [14] and $\Delta_{21} = 0.00008\text{eV}^2$ [15]. For simplicity we have set the charge lepton phases $f_1 = f_2 = f_3 = 0$. Since we have set the $\theta_{13} = 0$, the Dirac phase δ drops out of the zeroth order mixing angle. In table 1, we list the modified neutrino mixing angles for some sample value of a_1 and a_2 . Due to Planck scale effects, only θ_{12} have reasonable deviation and θ_{23}, θ_{13} deviation is very small less than 0.3° [12]. From table 1, 2, we used Co-bimaximal mixing [16,17], $\theta_{13} \neq 0^\circ = 10^\circ, \theta_{23} = \frac{\pi}{4}, \tan\theta_{12}^2 = \frac{1-3\sin\theta_{13}^2}{2}, \theta_{12} = 34^\circ$ and Dirac phase $\delta = \pm \frac{\pi}{2}$. We get the non-zero value of modified mixing angle $\theta'_{13} < 0.3^\circ$, gives non zero value. Due to Planck scale effects, non zero value of mixing angle θ_{13} indicates the possible CP violation in neutrino sector.

Table 1: The modified mixing angles term for various value of phases. Input value are $\Delta_{31} = 0.002\text{eV}^2$ [14], $\Delta_{21} = 0.00008\text{eV}^2$, mixing angle $\theta_{13} \neq 0^\circ = 10^\circ, \theta_{23} = \frac{\pi}{4}, \tan\theta_{12}^2 = \frac{1-3\sin\theta_{13}^2}{2}, \theta_{12} = 34^\circ$ and Dirac phase $\delta = + \frac{\pi}{2}$.

a_1	a_2	θ'_{12} in degrees	θ'_{23} in degrees	θ'_{13} in degrees	J'_{cp}
0°	0°	37.15	45.00	10.00	3.65×10^{-4}
0°	45°	36.46	44.96	9.94	3.56×10^{-4}
0°	90°	33.99	44.87	9.96	3.36×10^{-4}
0°	135°	34.80	44.91	10.02	3.48×10^{-4}
0°	180°	37.15	45.00	10.00	3.65×10^{-4}
45°	0°	36.34	45.04	9.87	3.50×10^{-4}
45°	45°	35.59	45.00	9.81	3.41×10^{-4}
45°	90°	33.19	44.91	9.84	3.21×10^{-4}
45°	135°	34.07	44.95	9.90	3.33×10^{-4}
45°	180°	36.34	45.04	9.87	3.50×10^{-4}
90°	0°	34.00	45.12	9.93	3.48×10^{-4}
90°	45°	33.31	45.08	9.87	3.21×10^{-4}
90°	90°	31.07	45.00	9.89	3.14×10^{-4}
90°	135°	31.86	45.03	9.95	3.34×10^{-4}
90°	180°	34.00	45.12	9.93	3.45×10^{-4}
135°	0°	34.66	45.08	10.05	3.38×10^{-4}
135°	45°	34.03	45.05	9.99	3.17×10^{-4}
135°	90°	31.72	44.96	10.02	3.28×10^{-4}
135°	135°	32.45	45.00	10.08	3.48×10^{-4}
135°	180°	34.66	45.08	10.05	3.45×10^{-4}
180°	0°	37.15	45.00	10.00	3.56×10^{-4}
180°	45°	36.46	44.96	9.94	3.36×10^{-4}
180°	90°	33.99	44.87	9.96	3.43×10^{-4}
180°	135°	34.80	44.91	10.02	3.48×10^{-4}
180°	180°	37.15	45.00	10.00	3.65×10^{-4}

Table 2: The modified mixing angles term for various value of phases. Input value are $\Delta_{31} = 0.002\text{eV}^2$ [14], $\Delta_{21} = 0.00008\text{eV}^2$, mixing angle $\theta_{13} \neq 0^\circ = 10^\circ$, $\theta_{23} = \frac{\pi}{4}$, $\tan\theta_{12}^2 = \frac{1-3\sin\theta_{13}^2}{2}$, $\theta_{12} = 34^\circ$ and Dirac phase $\delta = -\frac{\pi}{2}$.

a_1	a_2	θ'_{12} in degrees	θ'_{23} in degrees	θ'_{13} in degrees	J'_{cp}
0°	0°	37.15	45.00	10.00	-3.65×10^{-4}
0°	45°	36.46	44.96	9.94	-3.56×10^{-4}
0°	90°	33.99	44.87	9.96	-3.36×10^{-4}
0°	135°	34.80	44.91	10.02	-3.48×10^{-4}
0°	180°	37.15	45.00	10.00	-3.65×10^{-4}
45°	0°	36.34	45.04	9.87	-3.50×10^{-4}
45°	45°	35.59	45.00	9.81	-3.41×10^{-4}
45°	90°	33.19	44.91	9.84	-3.21×10^{-4}
45°	135°	34.07	44.95	9.90	-3.33×10^{-4}
45°	180°	36.34	45.04	9.87	-3.50×10^{-4}
90°	0°	34.00	45.12	9.93	-3.48×10^{-4}
90°	45°	33.31	45.08	9.87	-3.21×10^{-4}
90°	90°	31.07	45.00	9.89	-3.14×10^{-4}
90°	135°	31.86	45.03	9.95	-3.34×10^{-4}
90°	180°	34.00	45.12	9.93	-3.45×10^{-4}
135°	0°	34.66	45.08	10.05	-3.38×10^{-4}
135°	45°	34.03	45.05	9.99	-3.17×10^{-4}
135°	90°	31.72	44.96	10.02	-3.28×10^{-4}
135°	135°	32.45	45.00	10.08	-3.48×10^{-4}
135°	180°	34.66	45.08	10.05	-3.45×10^{-4}
180°	0°	37.15	45.00	10.00	-3.56×10^{-4}
180°	45°	36.46	44.96	9.94	-3.36×10^{-4}
180°	90°	33.99	44.87	9.96	-3.43×10^{-4}
180°	135°	34.80	44.91	10.02	-3.48×10^{-4}
180°	180°	37.15	45.00	10.00	-3.65×10^{-4}

From Table 1, one may consider a deviation from the exact co-bimaximal neutrino mixing matrix and gives and gives $\theta_{13} \neq 0$, indicates the CP violation. Since the CP phase δ is an independent parameter, with our present knowledge of mixing matrix $U\nu$. We can compute the maximum J_{cp}^m , by choosing $\delta = \frac{\pi}{2}$. We obtained J_{cp}^m , at various non zero value of mixing angle. The result are shown in Table 1, from the Table 2, we can put a limit on the amount of CP violating from the non zero value of θ'_{13} ,

$$J_{cp}^m = 3.65 \times 10^{-4} \tag{22}$$

4. Conclusions

We assume that the main part of neutrino masses and mixing from GUT scale operator. We considered these to be 0th order quantities. The gravitational interaction of lepton field with SM Higgs field give rise to a $SU(2)_L \times U(1)$ invariant dimension-5 effective Lagrangian give originally by Weinberg [10]. On electroweak symmetry breaking this operators leads to additional mass terms. We

considered these to be perturbation of GUT scale mass terms. We compute the first order correction to neutrino mass eigenvalue and mixing angles. In [13], it was shown that the change in θ_{13}, θ_{23} is very small (less than 0.3°) but the change in θ_{12} can be substantial about $\pm 3^\circ$. To summarize, we have shown that, due to Planck scale effects, it is possible to estimate the maximum allowed value of the Jarlskog invariant measure of CP violation. Since the CP violation is an independent parameter, one can assume a maximum value of unity for this quantity to measure the Jarlskog invariant, CP violating parameter. In Cobimaximal mixing model of neutrino mass matrix, this measure J_{cp}^{max} vanish implying no CP violating. Due to quantum gravity (Planck scale) effects gives non zero value of $\theta_{13} \neq 0$, it is possible to have CP violation.

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